

Dipeptidyl peptidase IV : regional and subcellular distribution in goat brain

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Dipeptidyl peptidase IV, an important serine proteinase, has been identified in the goat brain tissue. It shows a pH optimum of 7.45 in crude extracts. The regional and subcellular distribution of this proteinase is established in goat brain. The cerebrum portion of the brain has maximum percent activity followed by cerebellum, medulla oblongata, pons-varolli, thalamus, pituitary body and hypothalamus. In terms of activity per gram wet tissue weight, pituitary body is found to have the highest activity. The subcellular localization studies indicate its cytosolic origin in the brain.

Dipeptidyl peptidase IV [EC 3.4.14.5] is a serine protease that preferentially liberates X-proline or sometimes X-alanine dipeptides from the N-termini of some polypeptides¹ at pH 7.8–8.7. DPP IV is one of the very few proteinase which degrade the peptide bond in which the carbonyl group is provided by Pro. This protease degrades² several biologically active peptides, cytokines and hormones such as substance P (Arg-Pro-Lys-Pro-Gln-Gln-Phe-Phe-Gly-Leu-Met-NH₂), interleukin-8 (IL-8), growth hormone-releasing hormone (GH-RH), gastrin releasing peptides, α -chain of human chorionic gonadotropin (HCG) and neuropeptide Y which indicate its important role in regulatory processes. In addition, it plays a role in cell matrix adhesion through specific interaction with fibronectin and collagen³ and in the T-cell activation⁴. This protease is also involved in various diseases⁵. It has been purified from various mammalian tissues and body fluids such as kidney^{6,7}, liver^{7,8}, submaxillary gland⁹, seminal plasma¹⁰ and serum¹¹. Studies pertaining to this protease in brain have not been undertaken so far. In this communication, we report the presence, subcellular and regional distribution of DPP IV in goat brain.

Results and Discussion

The DPP IV activity has traditionally been assayed with a synthetic substrate Gly-Pro-4m β NA where the released 4-methoxy- β -naphthylamine is quantitated fluorometrically¹². Due to non-availability of a fluorometer, a simple colorimetric assay was devised for DPP IV where the released 4-methoxy- β -naphthylamine was coupled with Fast Garnet GBC dye (Scheme 1). In the present method, the enzymatic reaction was stopped by lowering the pH to 4.0 (by adding 1.0 M sodium acetate buffer pH 4.0) where DPP IV has no activity. And also this low pH did not interfere with the coupling reaction of 4-methoxy- β -naphthylamine with Fast Garnet GBC to yield a red colour to be estimated

at 520 nm. The free serine residue(s) at the active site also did not interfere with the coupling reaction unlike thiol, CH₂SH group¹³.

This colorimetric assay when used for assaying the DPP IV activity of goat brain in the pH range 5.0–10.0, gave a pH optimum 7.45 for DPP IV.

After determination of pH optimum, this colorimetric assay method was used for determination of subcellular and regional distribution of this enzyme in goat brain. The enzyme DPP IV was found to reside in the soluble fraction (also called cytosolic fraction) of goat brain because 68% of the total activity of DPP IV was present in this fraction (Table 1). A considerable amount of DPP IV activity was also observed in nuclear (20%) and mitochondrial-lysosomal (12%) fractions. However, the activity of DPP IV in nuclear and mitochondrial-lysosomal fraction can be due to the presence of intact cells in the nuclear fraction and incomplete washing of the mitochondrial-lysosomal fraction, respectively. Its subcellular localization was determined in comparison to cathepsin B [EC 3.4.22.1] which is a well known lysosomal cysteine proteinase¹⁴. The cytosolic origin of DPP IV has been reported by several workers¹⁵.

Further, the localization of this protease in different regions of the brain was also determined by separating it into different parts : cerebrum, cerebellum, pons-varolli, thalamus, hypothalamus, medulla oblongata and pituitary body. The cerebrum was found to contain maximum percent activity followed by cerebellum, medulla oblongata, pons-varolli, thalamus, pituitary body and hypothalamus (Fig. 1). Though cerebrum contains the highest percentage of total DPP IV activity because of its largest size, but pituitary body was found to have the highest activity in terms of per gram wet tissue weight (density of enzyme) followed by pons-varolli, medulla oblongata, cerebellum, thalamus, ce-

Table 1. Subcellular distribution of DPP IV in goat brain

Fraction	Total vol. (ml)	Activity/min/ml (units)	Total activity (units)	% Activity
Homogenate	105	3.666	384.93	-
Nuclear (N)	48	1.833	87.98	20.00
Mitochondrial-lysosomal (M-L)	48	1.099	52.75	12.00
Soluble (S)	80	3.721	297.74	67.90

rebrum and hypothalamus (Fig. 2). Pituitary body being the master gland of brain tissue, controls and regulates the secretion of hormones to coordinate functions of different parts

Fig. 1. Regional distribution (%) of DPP IV in goat brain.

of the body. The heavy concentration of DPP IV in terms of activity per gram wet tissue weight in pituitary gland may be suggestive of a major role for this protease in peptide processing.

Experimental

Fresh goat brain tissue removed from the freshly sacrificed goat was used in all the experiments. Glycyl-Prolyl-4-methoxy- β -naphthylamide (Gly-Pro-4m β NA) (Bachem) was used as substrate to measure the activity of DPP IV. Fast Garnet GBC (o-aminoazotoluene diazonium salt) and 4-

Fig. 2. Regional distribution (per g wet tissue weight) of DPP IV in goat brain.

methoxy- β -naphthylamine (both Sigma) were used as coupling reagent and standard, respectively. A refrigerated IEC-25 centrifuge was used for subcellular fractionation and a table-top Remi R8C centrifuge was used for the routine centrifugation. An EC 5611 pH meter was used. The absorbance was recorded by using an EC spectrophotometer.

Enzyme homogenate : Fresh goat brain was chopped into small pieces after removing blood capillaries and was then homogenized (10%, w/v) in glass-distilled cold water containing 0.1% Triton X-100 three times for a period of 15 s each time. The homogenate was stored at 4° and used as source of enzyme for the experiments.

Assay of DPP IV : A simple colorimetric method for estimating DPP IV activity in crude brain extract was used. The enzyme homogenate (0.5 ml) was added to the assay buffer (1.5 ml; 0.5 M Tris-HCl, pH 7.45) and pre-incubated for 5 min at 40°. The enzymatic reaction was started by adding the substrate stock solution (50 μ l, Gly-Pro-4m β NA, 10 mg/ml DMSO). After 60 min incubation, the reaction was stopped by adding stopping reagent (1.0 ml; 1 M sodium acetate buffer, pH 4.0) and then Fast Garnet GBC (1.0 ml; 1.0 mg/ml in H₂O). After 10 min, the red colored dye was extracted with *n*-butanol (4.0 ml) and estimated at 520 nm. Both enzyme and substrate blanks were also included, where these were added to the reaction mixture after terminating the reaction. The absorbance at 520 nm was then converted into activity units as nanomoles of 4-methoxy- β -naphthyl-amine liberated per min per ml enzyme homogenate at 40° by using the equation,

$$\text{Activity (nanomoles/min/ml)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{520} \times 4.0 \times 10^{-3} \times 10^9 \times 2}{\epsilon t}$$

where, ϵ is the molar extinction coefficient of 4-methoxy- β -naphthylamine (equal to 36600 under the assay conditions), t the reaction time (min), 4×10^{-3} the volume of *n*-butanol (lit) used for extracting the red color, 2 the multiplication factor for calculating the enzyme activity per ml, as 500 μ l of enzyme solution was used for reaction, and 10^9 is used for converting moles into nanomoles.

Subcellular fractionation : For subcellular localization of DPP IV, the fresh goat brain was homogenized in cold 0.25 M sucrose solution in a Remi glass homogenizer operating at moderate speed. This homogenate was subfractionated into nuclear (800 \times g, pellet), mitochondrial-lysosomal (16000 \times g, pellet) and soluble (16000 \times g, supernatant) fractions by differential centrifugation method¹⁶. Each fraction was then separately homogenized in cold distilled

water in presence of 0.1% Triton X-100 before measuring the activity of DPP IV.

Regional distribution : For determining the regional distribution of DPP IV, the fresh goat brain was first carefully separated into its different parts like cerebrum, cerebellum, medulla oblongata, thalamus, hypothalamus, pons-Varolli and pituitary body. These parts were then separately homogenized in cold distilled water containing 0.1% Triton X-100 and processed for DPP IV activity as above.

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